

AUSTRIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES

CoARA Action Plan 2026 -

Guiding Framework

PREAMBLE AND INTRODUCTION

About the Austrian Academy of Sciences

The Austrian Academy of Sciences (OeAW) is Austria's largest non-university institution for science and research. Its statutory mission is to “*promote science in every way*”. The Academy stands for fundamental research at the highest international level, evidence-based discourse, and the transfer of knowledge. Founded in 1847 as a learned society, today the OeAW has over 760 members, and 1,800 employees in 26 research institutes dedicated to innovative basic research, interdisciplinary exchange of knowledge and the dissemination of new insights with the aim of contributing to progress in science and society as a whole.

According to the various fields of activity (as research performing organization, as funding body and as learned society) the OeAW implements assessment procedures on three levels: on the level of the “research units”, on the level of “projects and programs”, and on the level of “individuals”. Basic principles – in line with the CoARA – of evaluations on all three levels are:

- independent peer-review by international experts (i.e. scientists not affiliated with any Austrian institution, identified and selected by independent bodies, like the international Research Board of the OeAW, the Advisory Boards of the institutes or the Foreign Members of the OeAW),
- orientation towards excellence,
- transparent procedures in compliance with high standards of ethics and integrity,
- consideration of particularities in the different fields of research as well as of various forms of research activities,
- commitment to a research culture of diversity, inclusiveness, and collaboration.

On one hand, the foundations for these principles are laid down in internal guidelines and rules, on the other hand, the OeAW affirms to be compliant to these principles on national and international level by the following activities: On national level the OeAW is a founding member of the **Austrian Agency for Research Integrity** (ÖAWI), which is an internationally recognized body standing out for high “*Standards of Good Scientific Practice*”¹. Furthermore, the OeAW is member of the **Austrian Platform for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation** (fteval) and insofar underlying its principles and standards².

¹ <https://oeawi.at/en/guidelines/>

² <https://fteval.at/en/prinzipien/>

On the international level, the OeAW signed the **San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment**³ (DORA) as well as the **European Charter for Researchers**⁴ and the **Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers**⁵. The OeAW has been an active member and Austrian representative of the **European Network for Research Evaluation in the Social Sciences and Humanities** (ENRESSH, EU-COST-Action⁶) during the project's runtime. By signing the **European Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment** and joining **CoARA**⁷, the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment, the OeAW has confirmed its strong commitment to international evaluation standards.

The OeAW is a member of **ALLEA**⁸ (All European Academies) which is a founding member and a key strategic partner of CoARA, as well as a member of **Science Europe**⁹. Science Europe maintains a leading and highly supportive stance toward CoARA.

As research performing and research funding institution, the OeAW supports excellent cutting-edge research. Research assessment supports this goal with international unbiased peer review on the prerequisite of freedom of research while unrestricted support is provided for curiosity-driven research.

³ <https://sfdora.org/>

⁴ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/charter/european-charter>

⁵ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/charter/code>

⁶ <https://enressh.eu/>

⁷ <https://coara.eu/>

⁸ <https://allea.org/>

⁹ <https://scienceeurope.org/>

Path to Implementation

Operational Steps

This chapter of the action plan illustrates how the OeAW will continue to promote and support the reform of research assessment. The action plan is to be understood as living document which will be updated regularly.

1. The Core Initiating Team (consisting of the OeAW/CoARA operational contact points) analyses assessment processes at the OeAW and nominates representatives from all relevant areas. Its aim is to establish a cross-functional group (“OeAW CoARA Group”) to coordinate, maintain, and support the implementation of the CoARA Principles.
2. The members of the OeAW CoARA Group will focus on selected areas that are most relevant to the institution with the objective of identifying potential for improvement and analysing current institutional practices in the evaluation of researchers and research institutes.
3. This involves a systematic review of internal policies and procedures, focusing on research assessment and evaluation criteria. Based on these results, the OeAW is continuing to implement the CoARA Core Commitments, and the Action Plan will be updated accordingly.
4. In addition, the OeAW is going to participate actively in CoARA Working Groups to exchange experiences, align with broader developments, and contribute to the advancement of shared best practices.
5. OeAW is contributing actively to the establishment of an Austrian National CoARA Chapter.

Accompanying measures

- Spreading the Idea
 - be active in the National Chapter
 - participation in CoARA Working Groups

Research Evaluation of Institutes – Example of an Internal Process

Illustrative Workflow

The OeAW conducts scientific evaluations of its institutes regularly – approximately every six years. The Department of Quality Assurance for Science and Organization (QA) at the OeAW is responsible for carrying out the procedure. The core principles of evaluations are as follows:

- **informed peer review** by recognized experts in the relevant fields as basis for the research assessment procedure,
- **standardized evaluation processes** across all disciplines while taking into account the **specific characteristics of different research fields** as well as the **diverse forms of research activity**,
- particular emphasis on **future-oriented questions** alongside an **excellence-oriented assessment** of research activities from recent years,
- **focus on the working group** leading to input on the further development of the **institutes' research strategy**,
- promotion of **young scientists**,
- **exclusion of quantitative indicators**, including the h-index and the Journal Impact Factor, or **ranking of organizations** in the assessment processes,
- no assessments at the **level of individual researchers**.